

A Research On The Environmental Sensitivity Of Preschool Teachers

Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Çevresel Duyarlılıkları Üzerine Bir Araştırma

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ÖZET

Okul öncesi öğretmenlerinin çevresel duyarlılıkları ve çevre bilinçli tüketicilik düzeylerinin incelenmesi amacıyla yapılan bu çalışmada ilişkisel tarama modeli kullanılmıştır. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu, 2017-2018 eğitim öğretim yılında İstanbul ili ilçelerinden; Beykoz, Kadıköy, Üsküdar, Küçükçekmece, Ümraniye, Sancaktepe, Çekmeköy, Beşiktaş, Ataşehir, Maltepe, Güngören, Sarıyer ilçelerinde Milli Eğitim Bakanlığına bağlı resmi ve özel anaokulları ile ilköğretime bağlı anasınıflarında görev yapan 278'i kadın 25'i erkek olmak üzere 303 okul öncesi öğretmeni oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada veri toplama aracı olarak Yeşilyurt, Gül ve Demir (2013) tarafından geliştirilen "Çevre Bilinçli ve Çevresel Duyarlılık Ölçeği" ile Ay ve Ecevit (2005) tarafından hazırlanan "Çevre Bilinçli Tüketicilik Anketi"nden yararlanılarak geliştirilen "Çevre Bilinçli Tüketicilik Ölçeği" kullanılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Çevre, Eğitim, Okul, Öğretmen.

ABSTRACT

In this research, a relational survey model was used to investigate the environmental sensitivities and environmental conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers. The research was conducted in Beykoz, Kadikoy, Uskudar, Kucukcekmece, Umraniye, Sancaktepe, Cekmekoy, Besiktas, Atasehir, Maltepe, Gungoren, Sariyer districts of Istanbul in 2017-2018 academic year. The sample consists of 303 preschool teachers (278 female and 25 male) working in public and private kindergartens and kindergartens affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in these districts. In the research, the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Awareness Scale developed by Yeşilyurt, Gül and Demir (2013) and the Environmental Awareness Scale prepared by Ay and Ecevit (2005) were used.

Key Words: Environmental, Education, School, Teacher.

INTRODUCTION

With the increasing global population reaching nearly 8 billion according to 2019 data, the needs of humanity are growing every day. As these needs increase, the environmental damage caused by humanity to meet these needs is reaching more serious proportions each day. Therefore, this problem has become a universal issue that concerns the entire world population (Baykal and Baykal, 2008). The current pace of industrialization and the efforts of developing countries to reach the level of developed countries are exacerbating environmental degradation. In the struggle between nature and humankind, it is believed that the fighting power of nature is decreasing day by day. As a result, disruptions in seasonal transitions, melting glaciers leading to rising sea levels, pollution of seas and lakes, air we breathe becoming harmful to health, exposure to noise, concrete, and metal pollution are being encountered (The World Bank, 2008).

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The most significant environmental problems in today's world are climate change, air and water pollution well beyond normal limits, chemical accidents, and the transportation of chemical waste (Sonnenfeld and Mol, 2002). With environmental problems making people's lives more difficult and threatening their continuity, human beings have started to work on the sustainability of natural resources and take various measures to protect the environment (WCED, 1987). One of the measures taken is environmental education. Environmental education is essential for societies today to leave a reliable, healthy environment for future generations to live in without concern. Therefore, environmental education holds critical importance in making future generations more sensitive to ensure they live in a safe environment.

Environmental education is defined as education aimed at creating awareness about the environment and its protection from birth to death (Dikmen, 1993; Act. Güngör and Ogelman 2015). Environmental education can be seen as a field of work that aims to create an environmentally conscious citizenship (Gülay and Öznacar, 2010). Starting environmental education as early as possible ensures the permanence of the education and the behaviors acquired. The qualifications of those delivering this education are undoubtedly as important as the quality of the education provided. Teachers are crucial role models for children. Therefore, the environmental awareness of teachers has a significant impact on the environmental sensitivity of children. Quality environmental education conducted by teachers in their classrooms forms the basis for the upbringing of generations sensitive to the environment.

When the literature on the subject is examined (Dhanyya et al., 2018, Franzen, 2017, Gkargkavouzi et al., 2018, Dobrinski, 2008, Erten, 2005, Öncü and Ünlüer, 2014, Şahin and Doğu, 2018, Tanık Önal, 2018), it is observed that research is generally related to subject teachers, class teachers, and teacher candidates. These studies aim to measure the perceptions of teachers and teacher candidates towards the environment, determine the qualifications of teachers providing environmental education, or determine their levels of environmental sensitivity. However, research on teachers' environmentally conscious consumerism levels is limited. No research has been encountered regarding the environmental conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers. The limited number of studies on teachers' environmental sensitivities and environmental conscious consumerism levels has increased the need for research in this direction. Therefore, it is important to determine both the environmental conscious consumerism and environmental sensitivity levels of preschool teachers. In this context, the aim of the study is to examine the environmental sensitivities and environmental conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers.

METHOD

This section of the research provides information about the research model, study group, data collection tools, data collection, and data analysis.

Research Model

This research was conducted using a relational survey model to examine the relationship between the environmental sensitivities and environmental conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers. The Relational Survey Model, one of the general survey models, is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables (Büyükoztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, and Demirel, 2008).

Study Group

The study group of this research consists of 303 preschool teachers, including 278 females and 25 males, working in public and private kindergartens and preschool classes affiliated with primary education institutions in various districts of Istanbul during the 2017-2018 academic year. The distribution of demographic information of the study group is given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Distribution of demographic information of the study group

Variables		N	%
Gander	Famele	278	91,7
	Male	25	8,3
Age	22 - 31	155	51,2
	32 - 41	115	38
	42 and above	33	10,9
Years of Seniority in Teaching	1 - 5 Year	96	31,7
	6 - 10 Year	122	40,3
	11 - 15 Year	50	16,5
	16 Year and above	35	11,6

Data Collection Tools

In this research, the "Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale" developed by Gül, Yeşilyurt, and Demir (2013) and the "Environmental Conscious Consumers Survey" developed by Ay and Ecevit (2005) were used along with the "Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale" developed by the researchers.

Data Collection

For collecting research data, the "Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale" and the "Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale" were used. The application was carried out through one-on-one interviews with preschool teachers. Before moving on to the application of the scales, a preliminary interview was conducted with the teachers to provide general information about the purpose of the scales and how they would be applied, and any questions the teachers had about the scales were answered. The scales were administered in the teachers' room during seminar periods when teachers were not with the children. The application took between 15-20 minutes.

Data Analysis

In this research, data collected with the "Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale" and the "Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale" were analyzed using the SPSS-17.00 software package. The normality test was conducted to determine whether the data obtained from the study group is suitable for normal distribution. Skewness and kurtosis coefficients are among the criteria that can be used to investigate the suitability of the distribution for normality. If skewness and kurtosis values are between +2.0 and -2.0, the distribution can be considered normal. The means, standard deviation values, skewness, kurtosis coefficients, and standard error values of the scores obtained from the scale according to the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 3.6 and Table 3.7 (Annex 2). Based on these results, Mann Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis tests were used since the data obtained from the "Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale" did not show a normal distribution. When the data obtained from the "Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale" were examined, non-normally distributed data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the research conducted to determine the environmental sensitivity and environmental conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers, the data obtained from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale and the environmental conscious consumerism scale of the participants in the study group were examined. The results were categorized under three main headings and interpreted.

Findings Regarding the Environmental Sensitivity Scores of Preschool Teachers

The Mann-Whitney U test results for the scores obtained by preschool teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale and the environmental conscious consumerism scale, according to gender, are provided in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Mann-Whitney U Test Results for the Scores Obtained by Preschool Teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale According to Gender

The dependent variable	Female (n=278)		Male (n=25)		U	P
	\bar{X}	ss	\bar{X}	Ss		
Environmental awareness	53,00	8,39	50,12	7,57	2447,50	0,01*
Environmental Sensitivity	87,71	16,30	82,40	15,96	2692,50	0,06
Whole Scale	141,70	22,72	132,52	21,92	2532	0,03*

*p<0,05

Table 2.1: Mann–Whitney U Test Results for Preschool Teachers' Scores from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale According to Gender

Upon examining Table 2.1, according to the Mann–Whitney U test results for preschool teachers based on gender:

Statistically significant differences were observed for both the overall Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale (U=2532; p<0.05) and the environmental consciousness subscale (U=2447.50; p<0.05) between females and males.

However, there was no statistically significant difference in the scores for the environmental sensitivity subscale between females and males (U=2692.50; p>0.05).

Similar to the findings of this study, previous research conducted by Öncü and Ünlüer (2014), Kışoğlu and Yıldırım (2015), Şahin and Doğu (2018), and Baş (2011) also found significant gender differences, with females scoring higher than males in terms of environmental views and environmental awareness.

Contrastingly, studies by Genç and Genç (2013), Gunindi (2010), Hassan and İsmail (2011), and Gkargkavouzi, Halkos, and Matsiori (2018) on teachers' environmental sensitivity did not reveal significant gender differences.

When examining the research related to Table 2.1, the differences in study groups, methods, and measurement tools used in the studies are considered to contribute to the varying results regarding the gender variable in environmental consciousness. Additionally, Kabaş (2004), in a study examining environmental research, highlighted that the sense of "responsibility towards nature," perhaps the most critical element of environmental awareness, is instinctively reflected in the behaviors of women due to their nature. Furthermore, women, who fulfill responsibilities such as providing food, ensuring food safety, access to clean water, and obtaining the energy needed for heating and cooking, may be more affected by issues like scarcity and deforestation, as well as irregular precipitation (Kabaş 2004; cited in Güneş, 2015). A review of the literature and research results suggests that women tend to exhibit higher environmental sensitivity compared to men.

Table 2.2: Kruskal Wallis Test Results for the Scores Obtained by Preschool Teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale According to Age

	Age	N	Average of Ranks	\bar{X}	H	P
Environmental awareness	22 – 31	155	141,94	52,79	4,20	0,12
	32 – 41	115	162,93	54,77		
	42 and over	33	161,15	54,03		
Environmental Sensitivity	22 – 31	155	144,65	86,03	2,38	0,30
	32 – 41	115	161,17	88,98		
	42 and over	33	163,00	87,12		
Whole Scale	22 – 31	155	142,36	138,82	3,92	0,14
	32 – 41	115	163,16	143,75		
	42 and over	33	158,38	141,15		

*p<0,05

Table 2. 2: Kruskal Wallis Test Results for Scores Obtained by Preschool Teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale According to Age

Upon examining Table 2.2, it is observed that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores obtained by preschool teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale based on age. This lack of significance is evident in the overall scale ($H(2)=3.92$; $p>0.05$), environmental consciousness subscale ($H(2)=4.20$; $p>0.05$), and environmental sensitivity subscale ($H(2)=2.38$; $p>0.05$).

Similar results were found in studies conducted by Mainieri, Bamett, Valdero, Unipan, and Oskamp (1997), Buhan (2006), Zaidat and Zaidat (2010), Dhanya, Shekhar, and Jaidev (2018), Şahin and Doğu (2018), and Karaca (2018), where the age variable did not significantly impact environmental sensitivity and consciousness.

In contrast, studies by Yeşilada (2009), Hassan and Ismail (2011), and Yılmaz and Yılmaz (2017) found that the age variable significantly influenced environmental sensitivity and consciousness. Yeşilada (2009) concluded that participants over 40 were more conscious than younger individuals, Hassan and Ismail (2011) found higher awareness among university students compared to teachers, and Yılmaz and Yılmaz (2017) identified the 51-60 age group as having the lowest scores.

The findings from this research and literature review indicate that while the age variable has been considered in many studies, different results have been obtained. In some studies, larger age groups exhibited higher environmental awareness, while in others, student groups showed higher awareness levels than teachers. This is thought to be related to teachers' levels of personal development and their participation in activities related to personal growth. Based on the results, it is suggested that the concepts of environmental sensitivity and consciousness should be approached from various perspectives in studies on the subject, considering the diverse results in research. The selection of different professional groups and different educational levels in study groups is considered to be influential.

Table 2.3: Kruskal Wallis Test Results for Scores Obtained by Preschool Teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale According to Professional Experience

	Professional experience	n	Average of Ranks	\bar{X}	H	P
Environmental awareness	1 – 5 yıl	96	146,23	53,26	1,76	0,62
	6 – 10 yıl	122	149,31	53,52		
	11 – 15 yıl	50	163,88	54,68		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	160,21	53,94		
Environmental Awareness	1 – 5 yıl	96	148,41	86,06	0,29	0,96
	6 – 10 yıl	122	152,55	87,75		
	11 – 15 yıl	50	155,96	88,52		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	154,27	87,11		
Whole of Scale	1 – 5 yıl	96	145,39	139,32	1,13	0,77
	6 – 10 yıl	122	152,17	141,26		
	11 – 15 yıl	50	159,67	143,20		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	158,59	141,06		

$p<0,05$

When Table 2.3 is examined, it can be observed that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores obtained by preschool teachers from the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale based on their professional experiences, in the overall scale ($H(4)=1.13$; $p>0.05$), environmental consciousness ($H(4)=1.76$; $p>0.05$), and environmental sensitivity ($H(4)=0.29$; $p>0.05$) sub-dimensions. Similar findings were reached in studies conducted by Buhan (2006), Ergin (2011), and Karaismailoğlu (2018), indicating no significant difference in environmental consciousness and environmental sensitivity dimensions based on professional experience. However, Baş (2011) found a significant difference among teachers based on professional experience, concluding that teachers with 11 years or more of seniority scored significantly higher in environmental sensitivity and environmental consciousness compared to those with 6-10 years of experience. No difference was observed among teachers with 0-5 years of experience.

Research results reveal varying conclusions among different researchers regarding environmental consciousness and sensitivity of teachers based on the years of professional experience. While many studies suggest no significant difference in environmental consciousness and sensitivity based on years

of experience, there are also studies indicating that those with higher professional experience are more sensitive and conscious (Baş, 2011, Erbasan, 2018). The choice of scales used in research on professional experience and whether the studied groups receive in-service training on environmental issues or engage in personal development training are factors that may contribute to the diversity of these results. Dhanya, Shekhar, and Jaidev (2018) emphasized the crucial importance of providing in-service training on environmental issues for teachers. Gkargkavouzi, Halkos, and Matsiori (2018), in their research in Greece, provided environmental education to teachers and found that after the test, the teachers' awareness level reached a higher level. Particularly, the percentages of choosing environmentally friendly packaging and having awareness levels of renewable energy were above 74% and 91%, respectively.

In light of this information, it can be said that receiving education on environmental issues during teachers' professional experiences and participating in activities related to the environment could enhance their environmental sensitivity.

Findings Regarding Preschool Teachers' Scores on the Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale

The results of the Mann-Whitney U test for preschool teachers' scores on the environmental conscious consumerism scale, categorized by gender, are provided in Table 2.4.

Table 2.4: presents the independent sample t-test results for the environmental conscious consumerism scores of preschool teachers based on gender.

The dependent variable	Female (n=278)		Male (n=25)		T	P
	\bar{X}	Ss	\bar{X}	ss		
ÇBTD Size	56,59	8,11	52,12	9,38	2,61	0,01*
ÇK Bottom Size	15,46	6,05	16,20	1,15	-0,59	0,56
ATE Bottom Size	21,12	3,09	21,00	3,48	0,18	0,86
Whole Scale	100,50	12,47	97,16	14,55	1,27	0,21

*p<0,05

When Table 2.4 is examined, the independent sample t-test results for preschool teachers on the environmental conscious consumerism scale indicate a statistically significant difference in environmental conscious consumer behavior sub-dimension scores for both females and males ($t(301)=2.61$; $p<0.05$). Additionally, according to the results of the independent sample t-test, there is no statistically significant difference for females and males in the overall environmental conscious consumerism scale, environmental concern, and perceived consumer effectiveness sub-dimension scores ($p>0.05$). Similar results are observed in studies conducted by Ay and Ecevit (2005), Nakıboğlu (2007), Hassan and Ismail (2011), and Gkargkavouzi, Halkos, and Matsiori (2018). These studies found no significant difference in environmental conscious consumerism related to gender. On the other hand, Yeniçeri (2009), Yaraş, Akın, and Şakacı (2011), Yılmaz and Arslan (2011), Alabay and Doğan (2015), Sayraç (2016), Saygılı et al. (2016), Sayraç, Arı, and Malkoç (2016), Dinar (2018), Şahin and Doğu (2018), Köylüoğlu and Acar (2018) found that gender had a significant impact on environmentally conscious consumer behaviors in their studies on this topic. These results suggest that women tend to be more conscious consumers than men, and this tendency is reflected in their purchasing behaviors.

In recent years, the active participation of women in the business world, increasing educational levels, and the consequent improvement in economic well-being are thought to influence conscious consumer behaviors. The growing variety of personal products targeting women and the increasing number of advertisements specifically directed at women on television may also contribute to this trend. Public service announcements and advertisements for eco-friendly products in the media sector are seen to influence the conscious consumer behaviors of women. The fact that both working women and housewives spend more time with television and other media tools implies that women are more affected by public service announcements and eco-friendly product advertisements. Therefore, when purchasing a product, women tend to pay more attention to details, considering impressions gained from public service announcements and environmental programs, and are more likely to choose the environmentally friendly option among two products with the same price and conditions. The one-way ANOVA test results for the scores preschool teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale,

including all sub-dimensions (environmental conscious consumer behavior, environmental concern, and perceived consumer effectiveness), based on the age variable are presented in Table 2.5.

Table 2.5: One-way ANOVA test results for the scores preschool teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale based on age.

Independent variable			Sum of Squares	Sd	F	P
ÇBTD	Age	intergroup	471,05	2	3,48	0,03*
		In-group	20315,69	300		
ÇK	Age	intergroup	127,04	2	1,76	0,17
		In-group	10816,61	300		
ATE	Age	intergroup	59,82	2	3,13	0,05*
		In-group	2869,59	300		
Whole Scale	Age	intergroup	496,54	2	1,55	0,21
		In-group	47884,20	300		

p<0,05

When Table 2.5 is examined, it can be observed that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores of the overall environmental conscious consumerism scale and the sub-dimension of environmental concern among groups based on the independent variable of age (p>0.05). However, a statistically significant difference is observed in the scores of the sub-dimensions of environmental conscious consumer behavior and perceived consumer effectiveness of the environmental conscious consumerism scale among groups based on the independent variable of age (p<0.05).

Table 2.6: presents the results of the Tukey test based on age for the sub-dimensions of environmental conscious consumer behavior (ÇBTD) and perceived consumer effectiveness (ATE) of the environmental conscious consumerism scale.

Variables	Age (i)	Age (j)	\bar{X} (i)	\bar{X} (j)	i - j	P
ÇBTD	22 - 31	42 ve üzeri	55,15	58,94	-3,78	0,05*
ATE	22 - 31	32 - 41	20,71	21,66	-0,95	0,04*

*p<0,05

According to Table 2.6, a Tukey test was conducted to determine the differentiation in the distribution of scores of the sub-dimension of environmental conscious consumer behavior (ÇBTD) of the environmental conscious consumerism scale based on age groups. Consequently, the average scores of the ÇBTD sub-dimension for individuals aged 22-31 (\bar{X} =55.15) are statistically significantly lower (p<0.05) compared to those aged 42 and above (\bar{X} =58.94).

Similarly, Table 2.6 reports the results of the Tukey test for the perceived consumer effectiveness (ATE) sub-dimension of the environmental conscious consumerism scale based on age groups. According to the results, the average scores of the ATE sub-dimension for individuals aged 22-31 (\bar{X} =20.71) are statistically significantly lower (p<0.05) compared to those aged 32-41 (\bar{X} =21.66). There is no statistically significant difference in the ATE sub-dimension scores among other age groups.

Research conducted by Yeniçeri (2009), Aracıoğlu and Tatlıdil (2009), Şahin and Doğu (2018), Karaca (2018), and Dinar (2018) reached the conclusion that age does not result in a significant difference in terms of environmentally conscious consumer behavior. On the other hand, Ay and Ecevit (2005), Nakıboğlu (2007), Yaraş, Akın, and Şakacı (2011), Boztepe (2012), and Biner (2014) found a positive relationship between age and environmentally conscious consumer behaviors in their studies. Çabuk, Nakıboğlu, and Keleş (2008) and Köylüoğlu and Acar (2018) concluded that younger individuals obtained higher scores than older ones.

Examining studies on the relationship between environmentally conscious consumer behavior and age reveals conflicting results. While some researchers find no impact of the age variable on environmentally conscious consumption, others suggest that as age advances, individuals acquire more environmentally conscious purchasing behaviors. Some studies even indicate a negative relationship between age and environmentally conscious consumer behavior. Therefore, consistent information regarding the relationship between environmentally conscious consumption or environmentally conscious purchasing behavior and the age variable has not been obtained.

Upon analyzing the results of this research, a positive relationship between age and environmentally conscious consumer behavior and perceived consumer effectiveness is identified. This positive correlation could be attributed to the fact that the entire study group consists of teachers from a single

profession, with similar education and income levels. The positive relationship between age and environmentally conscious consumption behavior might be associated with participants taking on more responsibilities as they age, meeting their family's consumption needs themselves, and being more careful and detail-oriented in their purchasing behaviors due to economic reasons. Additionally, as individuals age, an increase in environmental concern might lead them to prefer more eco-friendly products in their purchasing behaviors. The Kruskal-Wallis test results for the scores preschool teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale, including all sub-dimensions, based on professional experience are presented in Table 2.7.

Table 2.7: Kruskal-Wallis test results for the scores preschool teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale based on professional experience.

	Professional experience	N	Average of Ranks	\bar{X}	H	P
ÇBTD	1 - 5 yıl	96	149,35	56,21	2,72	0,44
	6 - 10 yıl	122	146,86	55,66		
	11 - 15 yıl	50	154,37	56,34		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	173,81	58,09		
ÇK	1 - 5 yıl	96	156,71	16,19	0,63	0,89
	6 - 10 yıl	122	151,31	15,39		
	11 - 15 yıl	50	144,76	14,96		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	151,81	14,94		
ATE	1 - 5 yıl	96	140,85	20,86	3,37	0,34
	6 - 10 yıl	122	155,98	21,04		
	11 - 15 yıl	50	166,81	21,72		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	147,53	21,14		
Whole Scale	Of 1 - 5 yıl	96	145,39	139,32	1,13	0,77
	6 - 10 yıl	122	152,17	141,26		
	11 - 15 yıl	50	159,67	143,20		
	16 yıl ve üzeri	35	158,59	141,06		

p<0.05

When Table 2.7 is examined, it can be observed that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores of the overall environmental conscious consumerism scale, as well as the sub-dimensions of environmental conscious consumer behavior, environmental concern, and perceived consumer effectiveness among groups based on teaching experience ($p>0.05$).

Similar to the findings of this research, Buhan (2006), Ergin (2011), and Karaismailoğlu (2018) concluded in their studies that teaching experience did not create a significant difference in environmentally conscious consumer behaviors.

However, Baş (2011) and Ahi and Özsoy (2015) reached the conclusion in their research that professional experience created a significant difference in environmentally conscious consumer behaviors. Baş (2011) found that those with 11 years and more experience exhibited more conscious attitudes and behaviors compared to those with 6-10 years of experience, while those with 0-5 years of professional experience did not show any difference. Ahi and Özsoy (2015) found that those with 16-20 years of experience obtained higher scores than those with 5-16 and 26 years and above experience. Those with 1-5 years of experience obtained scores similar to those with 16-20 years of experience. Despite obtaining significant differences from the findings, researchers emphasized that the effect size of professional experience was not very high.

Considering the research results and information obtained from the literature, it can be said that professional experience does not have a significant impact on teachers' levels of environmentally conscious consumerism. This result suggests that teachers not receiving any environmental education after starting their careers, and the environmental conscious consumerism being less prominent due to economic and life conditions, may contribute to this outcome. The correlation coefficients between the environmental sensitivity and environmentally conscious consumerism levels of preschool teachers are provided in Table 2.9.

Table 2.8: Correlation coefficients between the scales and sub-scales.

Scale	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Awareness Scale	-						
2. Environmental Awareness	0,84*	-					
3. Environmental Sensitivity	0,94*	0,61*	-				
4. Environmentally Conscious Consumerism Scale	0,48*	0,43*	0,43*	-			
5. ÇBTD	0,57*	0,53*	0,50*	0,82*	-		
6. ÇK	-0,04	-0,03	-0,04	0,43*	0,06	-	
7. ATE	0,27*	0,21*	0,27*	0,46*	0,27*	-0,09	-

*p<0,05

The table in Tablo 2.8 presents Spearman rank correlation coefficients depicting the relationships between environmental sensitivity and environmental conscious consumerism scales and their sub-dimensions among pre-school teachers. Statistically significant correlations, ranging between 0.21 and 0.94, indicate relationships from low to high levels. When examining Table 4.3, a moderate positive relationship ($r_s = .48$) is observed between environmental sensitivity and environmental conscious consumerism scales. However, the relationships between sub-dimensions, such as between the CK sub-dimension and the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Conscious Consumerism Scale ($r = -0.04$; $p > 0.05$), the relationship between the Environmental Consciousness sub-dimension ($r = -0.03$; $p > 0.05$), the relationship between the Environmental Sensitivity sub-dimension ($r = -0.04$; $p > 0.05$), the relationship between the CBTD sub-dimension ($r = 0.06$; $p > 0.05$), and the relationship between the ATE sub-dimension ($r = -0.09$; $p > 0.05$) are not statistically significant. Apart from these, all correlations calculated between other sub-dimensions are positive and statistically significant. Based on these results, it can be concluded that as the environmental sensitivity of pre-school teachers increases, their levels of environmental conscious consumerism also increase. These findings also suggest that as environmentally conscious consumption habits increase, individuals' environmental sensitivity and awareness also increase.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this section, the results of the research aimed at examining the environmental sensitivity and environmental conscious consumerism levels of pre-school teachers are presented, along with recommendations for pre-school teachers, educators, and researchers.

According to the results obtained from the research:

Significant differences were found between males and females in the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale in the overall scale and the environmental consciousness sub-dimension ($p < .05$). Specifically, females scored higher than males in both the overall scale and the environmental consciousness sub-dimension. However, no significant difference was observed in the environmental sensitivity sub-dimension based on gender ($p > 0.05$).

When examining whether the scores of pre-school teachers on the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale differ according to age and professional experience, it was determined that age and professional experience variables did not create a significant difference in the Environmental Sensitivity and Environmental Consciousness Scale and its sub-dimensions ($p > 0.05$).

The environmental conscious consumerism scores of pre-school teachers did not create a significant difference based on gender in the overall scale, except for a significant difference found in the CBTD sub-dimension between females and males ($p < .05$). According to this finding, females obtained higher scores than males in the CBTD sub-dimension.

When looking at the Kruskal Wallis test results based on age for the scores pre-school teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale, no significant difference was found in the overall scale according to age. However, statistically significant differences were observed in the CBTD and

ATE sub-dimensions of the scale. Analyzing which groups the statistical difference is between, it was determined that the CBTD sub-dimension scores of pre-school teachers aged 22-31 were significantly lower than the scores of those aged 42 and above ($p<0.05$). In the ATE dimension of the environmental conscious consumerism scale; the average scores of participants aged 22-31 are statistically significantly lower than the scores of those aged 32-41 ($p<0.05$).

When examining the scores pre-school teachers obtained from the environmental conscious consumerism scale according to professional experience through the Kruskal Wallis test, it is seen that the professional experiences of teachers do not create a significant difference in the overall scale and all sub-dimensions ($p>0.05$).

When the relationships between the total scores and sub-dimensions of the scales are examined according to the Spearman rank correlation coefficients, a moderate positive relationship is determined between the environmental sensitivity and environmental conscious consumerism levels of pre-school teachers ($r_s = .48$). It is also found that all sub-dimensions under the environmental concern sub-dimension are positively correlated with both the overall scales and other sub-dimensions. This summary covers the main findings in the text and provides an overview of the research framework.

REFERENCES

- Akçay, S. ve Pekel, O. (2017). Öğretmen Adaylarının Çevre Bilinci ve Çevresel Duyarlılıklarının Çeşitli Değişkenler Açısından İncelenmesi. *İlköğretim Online*, 16(3), 1174-1184.
- Akman, V., Akman, Ö., Ceyhan, A. ve Çelik, İ. (2016). Yeşil Pazarlamada Sürdürülebilirlik ve Dünya'dan Bir Örnek: Tchibo. *International Conference On Eurasian Economies*, 4, 278-282.
- Alabay, E. ve Doğan, Ö. F. (2015). Okul Öncesi Öğretmen Adaylarının Çevre Sorunlarına Olan İlgi Düzeylerinin Bazı Değişkenlere Göre İncelenmesi. *International Journal of Human Sciences*, 12(2), 34-50.
- Alpaslan, O.B. (2009). Çevre Hakkı, Çevre Hukuku ve ilgili AİHM Kararları. *Alpaslan Hukuk Kaynak*: <https://goo.gl/PiRC1X> Erişim tarihi: 8 Nisan 2018.
- Alisinanoğlu, F. , ve Kesicioğlu, O, S. (2009). Ebeveynlerin Okul Öncesi Dönemdeki Çocuklarına (60-72 ay) Yaşattıkları Doğal Çevre Deneyimlerinin İncelenmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 8 (29), 001-014.
- Altunkasa, F., Güçray, S., Uslu, N., Say, C. ve Yücel, M. (2008). Adana'da Çevre Duyarlılığı Düzeyinin Ve Geliştirme Olanaklarının Araştırılması. *Akdeniz Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi*, 19(2), 217-228.
- Annick, G. (2004). Can the Environment Help Boost Your Marketing? *Australian Journal of Dairy Technology*, 59(2), 85-89.
- Aracıoğlu, B. ve Tatlıdil, R. (2009). Tüketicilerin Satın Alma Davranışında Çevre Bilincinin Etkileri. *Ege Akademik Bakış*, 9(2), 435-461.
- Aslan, G. ve Karataş, A. (2012). İlköğretim Öğrencilerine Çevre Bilincinin Kazandırılmasında Çevre Eğitiminin Rolü: Ekoloji Temelli Yaz Kampı Projesi Örneği. *Zeitschrift für die Welt der Türken*, 4(2), 259-276.
- Atasoy, E. ve Ertürk, H. (2008). İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Çevresel Tutum Ve Çevre Bilgisi Üzerine Bir Alan Araştırması. *Erzincan Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 10(1), 105-122.
- Avcı, N. ve Toran, M. (2012). *Çocukluğun ve Erken Çocukluk Eğitiminin Tarihi ve Kuramsal Temelleri*. Ankara: Eğiten Kitap Yayınları.
- Ay, C. ve Ecevit, Z. (2005). Çevre Bilinçli Tüketiciler. *Akdeniz İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 10, 238-263.
- Aydın, F. ve Kaya, H. (2011). Sosyal Bilimler Lisesi Öğrencilerinin Çevre Duyarlılıklarının Değerlendirilmesi. *Marmara Coğrafya Dergisi*, 24, 229-257.

- Aydın, Ö. ve Aykaç, N. (2016). Yaratıcı Drama Yöntemi İle Verilen Eğitimin Okul Öncesi Öğrencilerinin Çevre Farkındalığına Etkisi. *Yaratıcı Drama Dergisi*, 11(1), 1-16.
- Aygün, B. ve Şakacı, B. (2013a). *Türkiye'de Çevreye Doğrudan Odaklı Çevreci Hareketler. Siyasal Ekoloji*. İstanbul: Otorite Yayınları.
- Aygün, B. ve **Şakacı, B. (2013b)**. Türkiye'de Çevre Konusuna Doğrudan Odaklı Çevreci Sivil Toplum Hareketleri Ve Çevresel Yaklaşımları. 38. ICANAS (*International Congress of Asian and North African Studies*), 1, 139-162.
- Baykal, H. ve Baykal, T. (2008). Küreselleşen Dünyada Çevre Sorunları, *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 5 (9), 1-17.
- Biner, N. (2014). *Tüketicilerin Yeşil Ürün Alma Davranışlarının İncelenmesi*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Trakya Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Edirne.
- Brause, J. A. ve Wood, D. (1993). *Environmental education in the school: Creating a program that works!* Washington, DC:North American Association for Environmental Education.
- Boztepe, A. (2012). Green Marketing and Its Impact On Consumer Buying Behaviors. *European Journal of Economic and Political Studies*, 5(1), 5-21.
- Bozyiğit, R. ve Karaaslan, T. 1998. *Çevre Bilgisi*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- Buhan, B. (2006). *Okul Öncesinde Görev Yapan Öğretmenlerin Çevre Bilinci ve Bu Okullardaki Çevre Eğitiminin Araştırılması*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Bülbül, H., Büyükkelik, A. ve Toksarı, M. (2010). Çevresel Duyarlılık Ve Yenilikçilik Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*. 15(3), 373-393.
- Can, A. ve Yalçın, F. (2016). Kentsel Sürdürülebilirlik Kavramının Arka Planı ve Bağlamı. Can, A. ve Dinçer, E.(ed.), *Esenler Düşünce Merkezi: Kentsel Yaşam ve Sürdürülebilirlik (17-51)*. İstanbul: İlbey Matbaa.
- Ceritli, İ. (1998). Araştırma Notları: Çevreci Hareketin Siyasallaşma Süreci. *Divan Dergisi*. 2, 255-270.
- Çabuk, B. (2001). *Okulöncesi Dönem Çocuklarının Çevre İle İlgili Farkındalık Düzeyleri*. Ankara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Ankara.
- Dedeoğlu, A. (2002). Tüketici Davranışları Alanında Kalitatif Araştırmaların Önemi Ve Multidisipliner Yaklaşımlar. *Dokuz Eylül İİBF Dergisi*. 17(2), 75-92.
- Dhanya, D., Shekhar, R. ve Jaidev, U. (2018). Determinants Of Environmentally Conscious Consumer Behavior. *Man In India*, 97 (20), 93-105
- Dımişki, E. ve Ünal, S. (1999). UNESCO – UNEP Himayesinde Çevre Eğitiminin Gelişimi ve Türkiye'de Ortaöğretim Çevre Eğitimi. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(17), 142-154.
- Dinar, N.(2018). *Yeşil Reklamların ve Çevre Bilincinin Yeşil Ürün Satın Alma Niyeti Üzerine Etkisi*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Dobrinski, L. N. (2008). *Views Of Environmental Educators On Teaching Environmental Education*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Queen's Üniversitesi, Ontario.
- Devlet Planlama Tekilatı. (1994). "Çevre Eğitimi, İnsan Gücü ve Katılım Planlaması". *VII. Beş Yıllık Kalkınma Planı*, Özel İhtisas Komisyonu. Ankara.
- Emekçiler, Ü. ve Yücel, M. (2008). Çevre Dostu Ürün Kavramına Bütünsel Yaklaşım; Temiz Üretim Sistemi, Eko-Etiket, Yeşil Pazarlama. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 7(26), 320-333.
- Erbasan, Ö. (2018). *Öğretmenlerin Çevre Okuryazarlıklarının Bazı Değişkenler Açısından İncelenmesi*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Afyon Kocatepe Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Afyonkarahisar.

- Erdal, H., Erdal, G. ve Yücel, M. (2013). Üniversite Öğrencilerinin Çevre Bilinç Düzeyi Araştırması: Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi Örneği. *Gaziosmanpaşa Bilimsel Araştırma Dergisi*,4, 57-65.
- Ergin, E.(2011). *Çevre Bilinci Geliştirmede Sosyal BilgilerDerinin Rolüne İlişkin Öğretmen Görüşleri(Elazığ İli Örneği)*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, Elazığ.
- Erten, S. (2005). Okul öncesi öğretmen adaylarında çevre dostu davranışların araştırılması. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 28, 91-100.
- Field, A. (2005). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS*. London: SAGE Yayınları.
- Franzen, R. E. (2017). Environmental education in teacher education programs: Incorporation and use of Professional guidelines. *Journal of Sustainability Education Vol. 16*, December 2017 ISSN: 2151-7452
- Genç, M. ve Genç, T. (2013). Sınıf Öğretmenliği Öğrencilerinin Çevreye Yönelik Tutumlarının Belirlenmesi. *Asya Öğretim Dergisi*, 1(1), 9-19.
- Hülay, H. (2011). Ağaç Yaş İken Eğilir: Yaşamın İlk Yıllarında Çevre Eğitiminin Önemi, *Tubav Bilim Dergisi*, 4(3), 240-245.
- Gülay, H. ve Önder, A. (2011). *Sürdürülebilir Gelişim İçin Okul Öncesi Dönemde Çevre Eğitimi*, Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
- Gülay, H. ve Öznacar, M. D. (2010). *Okul Öncesi Dönem Çocukları İçin Çevre Eğitimi Etkinlikleri. (1.Baskı)*. Ankara: Pegem Yayınları.
- Gülay Ogelman, H. ve Güngör, H. (2015). Türkiye’deki okul öncesi dönem çevre eğitimi çalışmalarının incelenmesi: 2000-2014 yılları arasındaki tezlerin ve makalelerin incelenmesi. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12(32), 180-194.
- Gülmez, M. (2006). Pazarlama Yönü İtibariyle Bilinçli Tüketim Ve Bilinçli Tüketicilere İlişkin Bir Saha Araştırması. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Meslek Yüksek Okulu Dergisi*, 9(1-2), 154 – 178.
- Güneş, G. (2015). *Toplumsal Cinsiyet ve Çevre*. Gültekin, L., Güneş, G., Ertung, C. Ve Şimşek, A. (Ed.), Toplumsal Cinsiyet ve Yansımaları, Ankara: Atılım Üniversitesi.
- Güngör, H. ve Ogelman, H. (2015). Türkiye’deki Okul Öncesi Dönem Çevre Eğitimi Çalışmalarının İncelenmesi: 2000-2014 Yılları Arasındaki Tezlerin Ve Makalelerin İncelenmesi. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12(32), 182–194.
- Günindi, Y. (2010). Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Çevre Dostu Davranışlarının Araştırılması. *TUBAV Bilim Dergisi*, 3(3), 292-297.
- Güzelyurt, T. ve Özkan, Ö. (2018). “Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Okul Öncesi Dönemde Çevre Eğitimi İlişkin Görüşleri Durum Çalışması. *Turkish Studies*, Doi number: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7827/TurkishStudies.13425> Volume 13/11, p. 651-668.
- Hassan, A. ve Ismail, M. (2011). The Infusion of Environmental Education (EE) In Chemistry Teaching And Student’s Awareness And Attitudes Towards Environment In Malaysia. *Procedia- Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 15, 3404 -3409.
- Hughes J. D. (2014). Environmental Problems of the Greek and Roman. *Maryland: John Hopkins University Press*.
- İlter, H. (2014). *Atık Yönetimine Sağlık Bakanlığının Yaklaşımı*. Yaşar Bağdatlı (Ed.), II. Ulusal Sağlık Kuruluşları Çevre Yönetimi Sempozyumu. (s.24-30). İstanbul.
- Jardins, J.R.D. (2006). *Çevre Etiği – Çevre Felsefesine Giriş, çev. Ruşen Keleş*. Ankara: İmge Kitabevi.
- Jamali, T. (2007). *Ekolojik Vergiler (Çevre Vergileri)*. Ankara: Yaklaşım Yayıncılık.
- Kagan, S. (2014). *The Practice of Ecological Art, Plastik Art and Science*, Erişim Tarihi: 05.04.2018, <http://art-science.univ-paris1.fr/plastik/document.php?id=866>.

- Kalburan, N., Kandır, A. ve Yurt, Ö. (2012). Okul Öncesi Öğretmenleri ile Öğretmen Adaylarının Çevresel Tutumları Yönünden Karşılaştırılması. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri*, 12(1), 317–327.
- Karabıçak, M. ve Armağan, R. (2004). Çevre Sorunlarının Ortaya Çıkış Süreci, Çevre Yönetiminin Temelleri ve Ekonomik Etkileri, *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 9, 203-228.
- Karaca, Ş. (2013). Tüketicilerin Yeşil Ürünlerle İlişkin Tutumlarının İncelenmesine Yönelik Bir Araştırma. *Ege Akademik Bakış*. 13(1). s. 99-111.
- Karaca, F. (2018). *Anne Babaların ve Okul Öncesi Grubu Çocuklarının Çevre Bilincine Sahip Olma Durumlarının Değerlendirilmesi*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Bartın Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bartın.
- Karataş, A. (2011). Çevre Bilincinin Geliştirilmesinde Doğa Tarihi Müzeleri'nin Rolü. *Akademik Bakış Dergisi*, 27.
- Kasimov, N., Malkhazova, S. ve Romanova, E. (2002). The Role of Environmental Education for Sustainable Development in Russian Universities. *Planet*, 8:1, 24-25.
- Kayaer, M. (2013). Çevre ve Etik Yaklaşımlar. *Siyaset, Ekonomi ve Yönetim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 1(2), 63–76.
- Keleş, R. ve B. Ertan (2002). *Çevre Hukukuna Giriş*, Ankara: İmge Yayınları
- Keleş, R. ve Hamamcı C. ve Çoban, A. (2012). *Çevre Politikası*, Ankara: İmge Kitabevi
- Keleş, R. ve Hamamcı C. (2005). *Çevre Politikası*, Ankara: İmge Kitabevi.
- Keleş, R. (2012). *Kentleşme Politikası*, Ankara: İmge Kitabevi.
- Kıışoğlu, M. ve Yıldırım, T. (2015). İlkokul ve ortaokullarda çevre eğitimi verecek olan öğretmen adaylarının katı atıklar ve geri dönüşüme yönelik tutumlarının farklı değişkenler açısından incelenmesi. *International Journal of Human Sciences*, 12(1), 1518-1536.
- Kızılaslan, H. ve Kızılaslan, N. (2005). Çevre Konularında Kırsal Halkın Bilinç Düzeyi Ve Davranışları (Tokat İli Artova İlçesi Örneği). *ZKÜ Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 1(1). 67-89.
- Konak, N. (2010). Çevre Sosyolojisi: Kavramsal ve Teorik Gelişmeler. *Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 24, 270–282.
- Köylüoğlu, A. S. ve Acar, Ö. E. (2018). Çevre Dostu Otomobil Satın Alma Davranışlarının Belirlenmesi Üzerine Bir Araştırma. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 10(2), 403-422.
- Mainieri, T., Barnett, E.G., Valdero, T.R., Unipan, J.B. ve Oskamp, S.(1997). Green Buying: The Influence of Environmental Concern on Consumer Behavior. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 137(2), 189-204.
- MEB, (2011). *Çevre Sağlığı Hava Kirliliği*. Ankara. MEB Yayınevi.
- Morgil, İ. ve Yücel, S. (1998). Çevre Eğitiminin Geliştirilmesi. *Bahçeşehir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 1(1), 76-89.
- Nakiboğlu, B. (2007). Tüketimin Çevreci Boyutu: Çevreci Tutum ve Davranışlara Göre Pazar Bölümlemesi. *Çanakkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 16(2), 423-438.
- Nemli, E. (2000). *Çevre Duyarlı İşletmecilik ve Türk Sanayinde Çevre Yönetim Sistemi Uygulamaları*. İstanbul: İstanbul Sanayi Odası, Çevre Şubesi.
- Ökmen, M. (2004). Çevre ve Politika. Marin, M.ve Yıldırım, U.(Ed.) *Çevre Sorunlarına Çağdaş Yaklaşımlar (327-368)*. İstanbul: Beta Yayını.
- Öncü, E. Ç. ve Ünlüer, E. (2014). Environmental view and awareness of preschool teacher candidates. *Procedia – Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 174(2015), 2653-2657.

Özçelik, R. (2006). Biyolojik Çeşitliliği Korumaya Yönelik Yapılan (Planlama ve Koruma) Çalışmalar ve Türkiye Ormancılığına Yansımaları. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi*, 2, 23-36.